

**Improving Outcomes In
Medicare Accountable Care Organizations:
Obtaining the Right Care, at the Right Time, in the Right Place,
at the Right Cost, by the Right People.**

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**A Literature and Data-Based Review of Possible Specific areas of
Recommendation and Process Improvement for the
USC Keck Medicare Pioneer ACO**

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• Background	Page 3
• Overview of Keck Medicare ACO Spending and Targeted Populations for Process Improvement	Page 5
• The Right Cost of Care is Critical to The Success of ACOs	Page 13
• Delivering the Right Care for Medicare Members	Page 19
• The Vital Importance of Delivering Care at The Right Time	Page 35
• Obtaining Care at the Right Place Really Matters	Page 38
• Receiving Care From the Right People Makes A Difference	Page 45
• Summary of Possible Process Improvements for the Keck Pioneer Medicare ACO	Page 48
• Citations	Page 56
• Annotated Bibliography	Page 66

Background:

In the United States, baby boomers are rapidly approaching retirement age, and the number of Americans who are eligible for Medicare coverage is growing significantly. As a result, the costs of caring for Medicare beneficiaries is progressively rising. At its current rate of cost growth, the Medicare program represents an unsustainable expenditure of spending -- both in absolute dollars and as a percentage of GDP. As a result, many have advocated the need to control or reverse Medicare's looming cost trends.

In an era of rising healthcare costs and greater expectations in quality of care, those responsible for the administration of health care organizations have much to be concerned with. While cost of care is becoming a critical consideration for all involved, additional initiatives are being launched by payers, governmental agencies and consumer advocacy groups to track measures of quality of care and patient satisfaction. Not only are metrics of quality, cost and patient satisfaction becoming publically reported, but significant financial penalties are increasingly in store for healthcare organizations that do not meet benchmarks.

In 2010, a component of the newly passed Affordable Care Act (ACA), instructed the Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS) to establish trial programs to attempt improvement in quality of care while lowering total cost for Medicare beneficiaries. Two such programs enacted were the Medicare Shared Savings Program (MSSP) and the Pioneer Accountable Care Organization. In both cases, participation by Medicare recipients is voluntary.

Of these two trial programs, the Pioneer ACO program has the greatest opportunity to achieve significant lowering of health care costs. While providing greater potential financial rewards, the Pioneer ACO program also places these health care organizations at risk should health care spending actually increase. For Pioneer ACO providers, an environment is created to truly stimulate change in healthcare patterns and practices.

Beginning in 2013, faculty physicians at USC's Keck Medical Center elected to participate as a pod in the Heritage Provider Network's Pioneer ACO. As such, Keck and its physicians became incentivized to lower total cost of care for its attributed Medicare patients, while attempting to simultaneously improve Medicare quality metrics. To achieve these goals, Keck will need to focus on one overriding vision: delivering the right care for Medicare beneficiaries, at the right time, in the right place, at the right cost, by the right people. If these goals can be achieved, then better overall care might be delivered at a lower total cost of care.

Overview of Keck Medicare ACO Spending and Targeted Populations for Process Improvement:

Initial review this summer of areas for focused cost reduction revealed many possible opportunities. There are isolated high cost patients, but many have unique circumstances that do not provide generalizable opportunities for cost improvement. If significant and long lasting strategies are to be developed for reduction in total healthcare spending, these strategies must produce broad improvements across many aspects of care. Over the long term, identifying and overcoming current aspects of healthcare delivery that broadly increase spending, represent opportunities for significant system improvement.

Initially, one might expect that a small population of patients might be prone to significant cost savings: those patients on very expensive medications, those receiving organ transplants, hemodialysis patients or those cancer patients receiving very expensive oncology medication at an early stage of treatment. Unfortunately, the opportunity for cost reduction in these groups appear surprisingly small (short of withholding care).

Over and over, review of the Keck ACO's Medicare spending data identified one group which represented not only a significant component of total Medicare cost, but also a group in which significant process improvement might produce dramatic cost savings: those patients receiving end of life care. An analysis of healthcare spending on

Keck ACO patients shows a well-known phenomenon. Total cost of care at end of life (EOL), represents a large portion of total Medicare spending.

In comparison to their age-matched cohort, Keck ACO patients dying in 2013 utilized a disproportionately large amount of health care dollars. As Table I illustrates, ACO patients dying in 2013 (n= 150) represented a total annualized Medicare expense of \$23,679,440 (1). In comparison to their age-matched control cohort, the total annualized cost of a similar number of age-matched living patients was only \$863,814 (1). And as seen in Table II, regardless of patient age, the last year of life represents a period of high health care cost (1).

More importantly, Table II illustrates an important finding. The potential opportunities for cost improvement are surprisingly found in the younger Medicare aged population. It might be theorized that these end of life patients are more likely to receive highly expensive futile care than their older and frail counterparts.

While it is undeniable that patients who are seriously ill, terminally ill or facing end of life care health challenges are more expensive, there is no doubt that this population also contains the greatest room for process improvement. Especially for patients approaching end of life, expensive treatments may be futile and represent a highly avoidable cost. Continued expensive treatments with little realistic benefit, does not benefit the patient and only contributes to these dramatic end of life costs.

Within this very expensive group of patients, opportunities for cost improvement are seen in many areas: home health, DME, skilled nursing care, avoidable hospitalizations, costly treatments without clinical benefit and wide variability of provider treatment outcomes. As such, this group of patients illustrate opportunities for process improvement for all Medicare ACO patients.

Providing care at the “right cost,” implies an understanding of the key determinants of total cost of care. One example is that of home health and DME. In 2012, Medicare spent \$18.2 billion on home health services (2). Studies have shown that there is significant variation throughout the United States in the use of home health and durable medical equipment (2). Additionally, there are significant variations in terms of billing by home health, and durable medical equipment providers within the same region or even city (2).

These variations cannot be explained by the patient’s underlying medical conditions, and truly represent instances of overutilization and overbilling. Depending upon how the home health agency bills, there is a significant potential for “gaming of the system” to increase reimbursement from Medicare (2). Patients with marginal needs for home health care benefit little from these services in terms of lower rates of

complications and hospitalizations, but represent a significant percent of total Medicare home health billings (2).

Identifying home health agencies that deploy sufficient resources for patients in whom clinical benefit will be derived, represent a good return on investment for Medicare (2). Medicare ACOs who can correctly identify these specific home health companies can achieve a positive return on investment for the ACO, and will help to lower total Medicare costs (2). Additionally, home health agencies who are willing to provide their initial evaluation of patients while still hospitalized, do a much better job at providing appropriate and efficient care with better outcomes in transitioning patients from inpatient to outpatient setting (2). Keck should seek to partner with home health agencies who are willing to provide in-hospital or in-office liaisons to facilitate good communication of home health needs and ensure that appropriate home health needs are met (2). The USC Keck Pioneer ACO must recognize that in order to ensure the success of the ACO as well as optimal clinical patient outcomes, the ACO must identify, and preferentially utilize home health agencies who provide higher value services.

The variations in cost (and sometimes even fraud) among DME providers is well documented (3). These excessive, and sometimes fraudulent charges for durable medical equipment are common especially in urban areas of the nation, where language barriers and lower patient sophistication may exist (3). Being an urban centered Medicare ACO, Keck might be mindful of DME costs among its attributed patients.

Although healthcare costs have continued to increase at an unsustainable rate, the leadership at USC Keck Pioneer ACO must understand that hospital-based care is one

of the most significant expenditures. With high infrastructure costs, increasing (expensive) technology and an aging population generating more care needs, hospital-based care is consuming a large part of the currently unsustainable U.S. healthcare spending (7). Not surprisingly, when previously hospitalized patients deteriorate after discharge and require repeat hospitalization, this is considered to be an expensive and avoidable failure of care which can impede the success of this particular ACO as well as the future of Medicare (1).

For these reasons, lowering rates of hospital readmission is fundamentally critical to providing care at the “right cost.” Unfortunately, the phenomenon of unintended hospital readmissions is not rare, and therefore is an important consideration for the leadership of health care organizations due to the financial burden it poses. Among patients covered by Medicare, nearly one in every five patients over the age of 65 will experience an all-cause (any reason) unintended hospital readmission within 30 days of a prior hospitalization (3). Nearly one in three Medicare patients will be rehospitalized within ninety days (3). Not only are these readmissions indicative of frequently avoidable harm to patients, but also are highly expensive -- estimated to cost the Medicare program well over 20 billion dollars in 2013 (23). Based upon the common belief that most hospital readmissions are prevalent, costly and largely preventable, this area is considered a potential source of great cost savings in healthcare for the USC Keck Pioneer ACO (5).

The governing boards of the USC Keck Pioneer ACO will likely need to look to new modes of organizational structuring and cost shifting if they are to structure delivery that is high-quality at a lower cost. Sharing ACO savings, payments and jointly

entering into new methods of reimbursement may be one way to help facilitate these goals (9). Although current financial ACO rewards may not be sufficient, ultimately new ACO models will more closely resemble global capitation. In future ACO models, health care entities may be justified in spending extra money on post-discharge care programs. It is probable that the saving from unnecessary rehospitalizations will more than support the increased spending on post-discharge care. This will also encourage governing boards to consider integration and alignment of both inpatient and outpatient care. Studies have shown that optimal hospitalization and post-discharge care require close clinical integration of both (13,14). In situations in which the two are unrelated, or under poor control, then post-hospitalization complications and high rates of readmission would be expected.

As Kenneth White and John Griffith point out in their text, attempts at paying physicians in a capitated or bundled payment method (that would include care provided for any complications or readmissions) would financially align physicians to minimize complications and maximize beneficial outcomes (14). According to the work of Arnold Epstein, “Although most interventions designed to reduce readmissions have focused on disease management and coordination of care, the most successful programs at reducing readmission are those that provide shared savings with an accountable clinical entity or structured payment incentives that are closer to that of capitation” (13).

Additionally, numerous research studies and pilot programs have shown that comprehensive post-discharge care programs are required to significantly lower complications and readmission (14). These programs are expensive and without reimbursement under traditional models of health care payment. To justify spending on

these types of programs, the finance members of the USC Keck Pioneer ACO's governing board will need to look for new models of reimbursement: not only to cover the cost of robust post-discharge programs, but as well to make up for the lost revenue from lower hospital readmission rates.

Unfortunately, the current model of reimbursement for most physicians and hospital systems does little to incentivize lower rates of hospital readmissions, complications and higher value care as opposed to higher volumes of care. The vast majority of physicians and hospitals are still financially dependent upon sickness to meet their bottom line. Ultimately, however, USC will need to move from volume to value. If it does not begin implementation of programs that will thrive in a capitated or bundled care environment, it might find itself obsolete to other local academic institutions. UCLA, for example, is far along in providing patient care and population health in a global reimbursement environment. Without beginning this transition, Keck and its ACO will not be able to sustain providing quality care at the "right cost."

The Right Cost of Care is Critical to The Success of ACOs:

While providing high quality care with associated high patient satisfaction is the ultimate goal of all healthcare providers, lowering cost of care is the fundamental imperative of an Accountable Care Organization. The primary directive for Keck ACO patients must be that care is provided at the right cost. The term “right cost” implies care which is simultaneously lower in cost and still high in quality. [This is where the concept of high value care (cost/quality) emanates].

To lower Keck ACO healthcare costs, one must be aware of general healthcare truisms. Analysis of Medicare cost data across the U.S. shows significant variation (15). Regions of high Medicare costs are largely due to over utilizations of services, higher billing practices and higher cost for services provided (15). Unfortunately and contrary to common thought, there exists no relationship between cost and quality (15).

Findings from the Dartmouth Atlas/ Brookings Institute studies find there are providers of high cost and low quality, and elsewhere high quality and low cost (16). Understanding this phenomenon would suggest Keck should become knowledgeable as to cost and quality outcomes data for all of its providers and vendors. Once identified by Keck, studies would suggest that increased utilization of these preferred providers would significantly lower total cost of care (15).

To truly provide care at the optimal cost, all providers must be aligned and incentivized. As the American Hospital Association has pointed out, current ACO and MSS programs do not motivate or reward hospitals to be true participants (17). For

example, lower hospitalization rates may lower total cost of care and benefit Medicare and the ACO, but negatively impact the bottom line of hospitals.

To that extent, Keck Hospital, its primary physicians, specialists, as well as the various Durable Medical Equipment and home health providers must be aligned in these goals. While Keck may not alter the rates of payment for these ACO providers, the development of preferred provider lists for the Keck ACO patients should be utilized.

For the Keck ACO, it is important to recognize significant variations in cost among Los Angeles area home health providers. As presented at May’s annual meeting of the California Association of Physician Groups (CAPG), the variation in Los Angeles home health costs by agency are great (23). As table III illustrates, the variation between the lowest and the highest costing home health agencies in Los Angeles are over doubled per patient cost (23).

As an example, Heritage Provider Network, possibly in association with other Los Angeles Pioneer ACO and MSSP's, might pool data on cost and outcome experience. Identifying home health companies who truly deliver risk-adjusted higher quality of home care with lower total costs, represents a significant opportunity for improvement in the Keck ACO. Recognizing and preferentially using these selected agencies would benefit all involved.

For frail, elderly, or patients approaching end of life, utilization of these high value home health resources by Keck physicians should be preferentially encouraged. It would be expected that increased utilization of these higher valued providers would produce significant cost savings to the Keck ACO pod. For home health agencies, DME providers or skilled nursing facilities, those of high quality with lower risk-adjusted costs should be rewarded by increased referrals.

Similarly, significant regional variations exist not only for Medicare spending, but also in the costs incurred for end of life care across the United States. Analysis of Dartmouth Atlas Medicare data suggests there are significant regional differences in the way end of life care is provided (16). Utilization of futile health care measures varies greatly by state and by region (16).

Studies have shown that the cultural bias, logistical barriers, and individual bias among treating physicians can significantly drive higher rates of expensive and futile care. As an example, a significant amount of the higher medical costs among Keck ACO patients who died in 2013 can be traced to a wide variety of factors. Specifically at Keck, failure to establish code status, lack of advanced directives, limited use of POLST forms when appropriate, failure to initiate hospice care prior to an acute hospitalization,

cultural barriers to the concept of palliative care and a wide variety of other avoidable factors were all observed in these expensive end of life patients.

Performance improvement might occur by tracking a series of metrics. For example, the percentage of patients with advanced directives, utilization of POLST advanced orders, initiation of hospice prior to hospitalization or percent of patients dying in the acute care center, might be ideal metrics to measure improvement.

Most importantly, Keck must understand its own unique “weak links,” that result in unnecessary expensive or futile care for Medicare aged patients. Understanding the factors that drive higher costs of end of life care would allow medical groups and ACOs to implement corrective strategies. Understanding the drivers for high rates of futile end of life care would help design implementation programs to lower this very high component of total Medicare spending which varies nationally (16).

Ultimately, the greatest factor to reduce cost of care within the USC Keck ACO will require alternate physician, hospital and vendor payment methodologies. The physicians that care for ACO patients must be incentivized to encourage value over volume. Perhaps internal faculty payment methods at Keck might address this and provide the correct incentive. Without this, reductions in total cost of care for Medicare patients may be difficult to achieve in the current CMS model of payment for volume (18). Perversely, the Keck Hospital would be financially harmed by reductions in avoidable hospitalizations, readmissions, and unnecessary procedures, treatment and imaging volume. Ultimately, Medicare costs will be most reduced only when innovative payment models such as bundled care or global capitation become available (18). These

payment models would allow a change in health care practice from that of payment for volume to that of payment for value (18).

Although these alternate payment models do not exist in the current version of Medicare Pioneer ACOs and Shared Savings Programs, it is likely that future versions will increasingly look like Medicare Advantage in terms of global capitation. Keck, its physicians and the ACO might be best served by developing a broader primary care base and becoming a Medicare Advantage provider. Being a primary care Medicare Advantage provider would have significant spill-over benefits to the ACO. Providing care within a capitation model forces providers to more accurately consider the value proposition of the care they provide and recommend. This type of payment model weans providers from the payment for volume structure to a payment for value mindset.

Across town, the UCLA Medical Group has very successfully built a large primary care base, and has transitioned to providing care under HMO global payment while still within the content of an academic and tertiary care setting. This is not easy, but USC will need to develop these same skills for its long-term future. These skills will be particularly important in payment models such as the financial environment of future Medicare ACO programs.

Initial results from Pioneer ACO programs across the nation show a wide variety of performance improvement interventions which have been shown to reduce total cost of care (19). This implies that the potential for reduction in Medicare fee-for-service spending exists if groups like the USC Keck Pioneer ACO are able to correctly identify and implement programs which will lower cost of care for its recipients, given its own particular institutional limitations and barriers (19). These new approaches to

healthcare delivery are not easy, but evidence suggests that achieving significant reductions in cost of care is possible if data is available, limitations are recognized and optimal resources and incentives are aligned.

Delivering the Right Care for Medicare Members:

It is of great importance that the USC Keck Pioneer ACO provides the “right care”: that which is timely, cost efficient and of high quality to its patients. Ideally, this high value care is delivered in a variety of settings: acute care hospital, subacute care hospital, skilled or non-skilled nursing, at home or within the outpatient physician setting. For best care to occur, all four of these components must provide optimal care with optimal communication and smooth transitions.

The first critical focus for the USC Keck ACO might be that of reducing unintended hospital readmissions. By definition, these are repeat hospitalizations that occur for any reason within thirty days of a prior hospital stay (5). As such, hospital readmissions are often felt to represent a failure in care. Whether it be due to inadequate care during the original hospital stay or complications following discharge, these readmissions represent potentially avoidable breakdowns in health care delivery. Unfortunately, not only are these readmissions a common phenomenon in American medicine, but are very costly and typically indicate potential impairments in the health care delivery processes (5). It should not be surprising that avoidable hospital readmissions were generally a common cost driver in the Keck ACO, and specifically in patients at end of life.

Unfortunately, the phenomenon of unintended hospital readmissions is not rare, and therefore is an important consideration for the leadership of all health care organizations. Among patients covered by Medicare, nearly one in every five patients over the age of 65 will experience an all-cause (any reason) unintended hospital

readmission within 30 days of a prior hospitalization (3). Nearly one in three Medicare patients will be re-hospitalized within ninety days (3). Not only are these readmissions indicative of frequently avoidable harm to patients, but also are highly expensive -- estimated to cost the Medicare program well over 20 billion dollars in 2013 (23). Based upon the common belief that most hospital readmissions are prevalent, costly and largely preventable, this area is considered a potential source of great cost savings in healthcare (5).

This may be particularly difficult for Medicare providers, in which a mixed message is conveyed. The system of payment created by Medicare may be part of the problem, not the solution (20). Hospitals are paid the same amount of money for a particular hospital related diagnosis, regardless of length of stay. Shorter and shorter hospital stays have been encouraged by hospital systems for years. Not surprisingly, a premature discharge, or incomplete care delivered during the initial hospitalization may therefore commonly be the unintentional result. And then if readmission should occur, hospitals are once again paid for this repeat episode of in-patient care.

For healthcare entities like the Keck ACO, elevated rates of hospital readmission play a significant role in generating higher than desirable total Medicare costs of care. Relative to statistics for a well-coordinated Medicare Advantage Program, Keck has significant room for improvement. More importantly, unintended hospital readmissions are global indicators of a potential breakdown in any number of aspects along the health care continuum. As such, unintended hospital readmissions might be a critical focus for the USC Keck Pioneer ACO. To achieve process improvement, however, Keck must focus

on each consecutive step in a patient's care, as the opportunities for improvement are not always obvious, and may occur far down the care continuum.

From a governance standpoint, however, consider this dilemma: For a limited number of diagnoses (at this time), readmission triggers a financial penalty under Medicare (21). For the remainder of diagnoses, however, Medicare reimburses full payment for these unintended readmissions. And for the vast majority of other payer types, readmissions are reimbursed as fully as the initial hospital stay. To the extent that readmissions fill hospital beds, and to the extent that a hospital's financial performance depend largely upon those beds being filled, governing boards will have a hard time embracing and financially justifying expensive resources to reduce hospital readmissions. Consider if hospital readmissions were to disappear overnight, the financial implications to most hospitals under the current payment model would be disastrous.

Hospital readmissions are of great interest to all affected stakeholders. For hospital-based organizations, increasing Medicare financial penalties will make readmission rates a growing financial concern. In an attempt to motivate hospitals to lower their rates of readmissions, the Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services have enacted financial penalties when Medicare fee-for-service patients require readmission (22,23). This Medicare program, known as the Hospital Readmission Reduction Program, was instituted under the fundamental belief that healthcare organizations can lower these rates of readmission, and therefore drive down hospital-related costs (23). Beginning in 2013, financial penalties were progressively enacted on those hospitals whose rates of readmission are deemed in excess of established benchmarks (8). The

number and scope of diagnoses that will make hospitals subject to readmission penalties are expected to grow over the coming years (24). Attention to the subject of hospital readmissions will be increasingly critical to the leaders of health care organizations (9).

Furthermore, for hospital organizations that participate in shared savings programs or Accountable Care Organizations, unintended hospital readmissions represent lost savings that might otherwise occur with higher efficiencies of care (13). For financially at-risk medical groups, capitated hospital organizations or integrated hospital/provider networks such as Kaiser Permanente, hospital readmissions represent significant and potentially avoidable costs. For employers who fund their workers' insurance premiums, for insurance companies who are at risk for unexpected costs, and for Medicare and Medicaid who must pay for the cost of care for the members they cover, these repeat hospitalizations represent an incremental unnecessary cost. As written by Kenneth White and John Griffith, these readmissions greatly impact the most important stakeholder, the patient (14). Not only do these complications affect lifespan and quality of health, but represent greater patient financial responsibility through their share of the cost of these undesired additional healthcare needs. For all of these reasons, the leadership of health care entities must understand how readmissions adversely impact each and every stakeholder.

Beginning with the acute hospitalization, Keck must attempt to ensure that optimal clinical care within the walls of the hospital is provided. Publications have shown that this is maximally achieved through the development of "care pathways," "care bundles" or clinical treatment derived from evidence-based guidelines (14). In relation to nationwide published hospital quality metrics, Keck might have room for

improvement. As research studies on three common hospital diagnosis has shown, (Pneumonia, Congestive Heart Failure, and Acute MI) uniformity of optimal care lowers cost, improves outcome and reduces frequency of later hospital readmissions (5).

In the case of pneumonia, studies show that rapid initiation of treatment with an evidence-based choice of antibiotics can reduce hospital readmission, improve outcome and lower total cost of care (15). As to congestive heart failure, hospital based quality initiatives rely upon not only use of evidence based treatment, but more importantly the education of patients and families regarding early warning signs of recurrent pulmonary fluid accumulation (16). This allows for early recognition and treatment of recurrent CHF after discharge, before repeat hospitalization becomes necessary. Identification and treatment of heart failure with evidence-based best practices reduces the rate of cardiac and non-cardiac related Medicare costs and overall complications (37). As an example, Keck patients with significant heart disease would be best suited for discharge to skilled nursing facilities or home health services who have demonstrated high levels of clinical competency for this condition. As such, overall Medicare costs would be expected to be lower for these patients (37). In regard to treatment of acute MI's, there are widely recognized critical factors during the acute intervention and upon discharge that improve outcome and prevent unnecessary and unintended readmissions (17). Keck might strive for one hundred percent compliance with these measures. As such, uniform treatment with care pathways and best practices will ensure that the USC Keck Pioneer ACO is providing optimal care: higher in quality and lower in cost.

While a hospital may develop strategies for a multitude of clinical conditions that are subject to treatment or prevention within the acute hospital setting, uniform

implementation always remains the challenge. While Keck has many care programs in place, review of its ACO charts show that delivery of this evidence-based care is not always achieved. Keck might continuously reexamine its own areas in need of focused improvement. Research has shown that formation of multi-disciplinary performance improvement teams has been shown to facilitate clinical improvement (14). To be maximally effective, these teams must include all clinical service participants, to focus on a shared opportunity for improvement. It is the role of these performance improvement teams to identify and disseminate these best practice guidelines for treatment. Data must be collected on a continuous basis to identify whom, when and why these guidelines are or are not followed. The barriers to usage must be understood, and the implementation adjusted to achieve higher rates of utilization. For example, review of care within the Keck ACO reveals challenges that other medical groups and ACOs may not face. This is a constant feedback loop that continuously refines the care process to achieve better and better outcomes. The implementation of these performance improvement teams within the USC Keck Pioneer ACO has the potential to ensure that all patients are provided not only the right care, but the best care.

Similarly, information management and clinical analytics have the potential to produce significant improvements in care (11). For example, Keck ACO patients frequently receive care from other hospitals, emergency rooms and providers. The absence of this clinical information seems to significantly limit the accuracy, reduce the efficiency and increase the cost of hospital-based care. For organizations like Keck, research has shown that automated systems that trigger best practice treatments in real-time, could improve quality of care and lessen complications (31). The opportunity

to use health risk assessment software prior to discharge may help uniformly identify those patients in whom intensive discharge resources may be highly beneficial. If a health-risk assessment was performed on all Keck ACO patients at the time of discharge, patients at high risk for post-discharge complications would be identified (32). This risk assessment tool could be used to guide additional home health or skilled nursing care and shorten physician follow intervals (32). All of these measures have been shown to improve quality of care and reduce costs (32). Based upon the robust support systems found in many health care organizations, resources and priorities can be allocated in an effort to anticipate clinical needs or complications before they become significant or costly. In this way, quality of care is improved. In the age of increasing electronic health records and order entering, strong support systems can be relied upon to reduce these post-discharge complications and potential readmissions. Many at Keck seem to believe that I.T. opportunities to impact quality and cost of care could be significantly optimized.

Not only must hospitals know how often readmissions are occurring relative to benchmarks, but relative to a wide variety of co-morbidities and demographic factors. Furthermore, in most hospitals where a wide variety of physicians and staff care for patients, the ability to further refine the data by providers is important: to understand who is and is not providing optimal care. To fill this void, a number of health IT companies have stepped forward. Commonly used hospital software such as Crimson, can not only compare readmission rates to benchmarks, but appropriately provide the statistical analysis to adjust them by age, sex, and other co-morbidities (33). Furthermore, these rates can be compared relative to the particular providers who direct care. In general, it will be hard for health care organizations to administratively

reinforce what's right about their care, until they have good data on what's wrong (26). Robust information management systems could allow the Keck ACO to have reliable data to statistically forecast which subset of diagnoses, co-morbidities or providers require the greatest attention in efforts to optimize quality of care, while lowering cost. Statistical analysis will allow creation of various cost vs. benefit analysis of a wide variety of possible new clinical programs.

For hospitals, however, the most challenging and frustrating aspect to reducing rates of readmission may often times be beyond their control. Studies have shown that care provided during the initial hospital stay may have less influence on the rate of hospital readmissions, than the care delivered after discharge (5). In a recent study examining hospital readmissions, the data reveal an unexpected finding. In the majority of cases, patients who reenter the hospital do so with a wide spectrum of conditions that often differ from their prior hospital diagnosis. As suggested by this study, Medicare aged patients are at a heightened risk for rehospitalization due to a wide variety of factors. The broad range of acute conditions responsible for readmission may reflect a 'post-hospitalization syndrome' -- a generalized vulnerability to illness common to many frail, elderly or end of life discharged patients (43). Many of these Medicare aged patients develop new impairments following the acute hospitalization (43). Some possible contributing factors may be generalized weakness and debility, nutritional impairment, side effects of treatment medications, loss of strength and mobility, altered mental status, and consequences related to post-discharge medication confusion (34,35). Despite the USC Keck Pioneer ACO's best efforts to ensure that they are

providing the right care within the hospital's walls, greater attention following discharge may be necessary in reducing many avoidable complications and costs.

As was seen in chart audits of previously hospitalized Keck patients, unintended hospital readmissions frequently stem from inadequate transitions of care, poor post-discharge communications, impaired coordination of post-hospital services and insufficient post-discharge outpatient services. These findings correlate with observations made elsewhere (36). Review of Keck ACO patient medical records show that important medical communication between those caring for hospitalized patients and the subsequent skilled nursing facility and providers, is frequently suboptimal. Important subtle and not so subtle priorities of treatment are frequently lost by those providing care at the next level. In fact, instances of actual documented conversation between discharging physicians and the new accepting physicians at subacute or skilled nursing facilities were not seen. The longstanding tradition of merely copying the hospital chart and sending it to the next facility, may not be sufficient communication for subsequent providers in many complex cases. The result of this limited communication includes avoidable errors, readmissions and higher cost of care. The same has been observed nationally (37).

To make matters worse, hospitals perceive that their involvement with the patient and family ends when the patient is wheeled outside the four walls of the hospital. Perhaps most importantly, who will the patient and family communicate with once they have been discharged? Hospital case managers typically do not involve themselves with the patient's care or problems once the patient has left the hospital. When inevitable problems do occur at home, however, who is the patient or family to

call? Even if available, hospital and post-discharge providers may not be sufficiently knowledgeable or equipped to deal with post-discharge issues. The result is avoidable complications or return trips to the ER or hospital. This offers an opportunity for the USC Keck ACO to step in and provide these services. Simply put, Keck ACO patients need a case manager they can speak with 24 hours per day, 7 days a week.

In one simple example that was observed in a patient with congestive heart failure, (who was discharged on home oxygen), the patient ran into problems when the oxygen was not delivered on time. In the absence of timely resources for assistance, it should not be surprising that this Keck ACO patient returned to the emergency room and was readmitted.

The administrative (and financial) challenge, of course, is that hospitals have perceived their role in patient care to end once the patient is discharged. No financial resources are typically provided by payers for hospitals to provide the ongoing post-discharge case management, which would be expected to significantly reduce hospital readmissions. As long as those in hospital-based clinical services view their relationship to end upon discharge, then readmissions will continue to occur.

Equally important is a clinical services assessment for each and every patient prior to discharge: an assessment of the individual factors that will provide barriers to care and medical challenges after discharge. Those in clinical services must anticipate multiple potential factors that determine post-discharge success or failure: who is going to help the patient upon discharge, the home needs upon discharge, transportation requirements to attend important post hospital follow up visits, barriers to discharge, impediments to safe and adequate care at home, family dynamics (are any of the family

members willing to help care for a sick or frail family member upon discharge?) and others. The unique post-discharge factors inherent in the patient's age, economic status, level of functioning, ability to understand discharge instructions, ability to seek and afford the appropriate post-discharge care, and underlying diagnoses must be anticipated by the discharge planning process. Understanding barriers and deploying available resources are critical functions of a health care organization's clinical services.

Once discharged, Keck patients might benefit from targeted post-discharge care. Research by Fortinsky and others have identified risk factors for complications following discharge (38). Identification of these independent risk variables by hospital case managers may allow for targeted increased post-discharge intervention based upon published literature: reductions in cost and complications would be expected (38).

Among Medicare patients, who are commonly elderly and frail, the quality, intensity and timing of post-discharge care is critical. This belief has been supported by the results of pilot programs that have provided more intense and multi-disciplinary follow-up for patients after discharge. These programs have shown that hospital readmissions can be reduced by comprehensive post-discharge care (39,40,41,42). From an administrative standpoint, post-discharge care may be as important as the initial hospital care itself in terms of lowering rates of readmission (42). For those responsible for the deployment of resources within the Keck ACO, the implications are clear. Hospital readmissions cannot be reduced if clinical services are only focused on the care provided during the acute hospital stay.

Similarly, studies have shown that targeted medical attention to skilled nursing patients at high-risk, will reduce complications and chance of repeat hospitalization

(32). Increased nursing services for these high-risk patients have been shown to improve outcomes and lessen complications (32). The presence of particular medical conditions should trigger increased acuity of care and resources. Although this might be somewhat more expensive initially, ultimately it has been shown to produce a positive return on investment by reducing avoidable complications (32).

These assumptions are also supported by studies in surgical patients.

Publications show that most readmissions after surgery are not always related to the surgery itself but often to the patient's underlying medical condition (43). Similarly, it is their debilitated state that places these patients at high-risk for complications and readmission. This explains why the most successful programs to reduce hospital readmission are those that are multi-disciplinary in approach, and provide close observational follow-up during this medically vulnerable post-discharge period (39,40,41,42). It is the provision of this type of care that can potentially improve clinical outcomes in a cost-efficient way.

As studies have shown, the ability to reduce hospital readmissions lies in a multitude of factors. No improvements, however, can be made without the ability to gather useful data. At their most basic level, measurement of readmissions must occur. This is particularly challenging for the Keck ACO as care commonly occurs elsewhere. Readmissions might occur at a different hospital or health system than where the original hospitalization occurred. Without these other facilities sharing clinical data, it will be difficult to know whether a wide number of administrative interventions are producing the type of hospital care that leaves the patient less prone to complications and readmission.

Studies have also identified another key clinical service to reduce preventable hospital readmissions: comprehensive discharge planning (44). One simple example of this is the process of discharge medication reconciliation –making sure that the medications taken by the patient after discharge are the ones intended, and not confused with other prior discontinued medications. For example, studies have shown that confusion over medication at time of discharge creates an increased likelihood of later medication side effects, and inadequate treatment of the initial hospitalization issue (45). This is especially true in the elderly where confusion regarding multiple medications may be likely. A simple home medication reconciliation process has been shown to improve compliance with critical meds, decrease chances of unintended side effects and lower the risk of the patient taking prior unintended medications simultaneously (46).

Reducing these subsequent unintended hospital readmission is significant as readmission rates are now publically reported (26). For the decision makers of health care organizations like the USC Keck Pioneer ACO, this is an important concern. Publication of these readmission rates will likely affect the organization’s reputation, not just in this one area, but broadly for its service excellence across all aspects of the health care entity. As emphasized by Berry and Seltman, the positive public perception of a healthcare organization’s brand is highly valuable, and should be protected (46). This effect on the brand may cause patients to compare competing healthcare organizations based upon this public reporting: adversely impacting a health care organization’s ability to recruit and retain their patient base. Not surprisingly, being able to impact the rate of unintended readmissions following discharge has become imperative for many

involved with the administration of healthcare organizations, whether they be hospitals, medical groups, payers or federal healthcare organizations (26).

From a governance standpoint, healthcare organizations must first decide what priority they will place on reducing hospital readmissions. The setting of organizational priorities and allocation of financial resources in this area falls in the domain of the governing body. While the reduction of post-discharge complications would seem to be a highly desirable goal from many standpoints, the costs to do this are not insignificant. More importantly, the current differing models of health care reimbursement produce conflicting incentives that the financial management of healthcare organizations must take into consideration. To date, “the penalties currently in place, and the difficulties in restructuring health care organizations, seem to have provided little meaningful motivation so far to significantly reduce readmissions” (20). Furthermore, Medicare’s approach is not being warmly accepted. As reported in the New York Times, the governing boards of “academic medical centers are complaining that the penalties do not take into account the extra challenges posed by extremely sick and low income patients – those at higher risk for readmission” (20).

Ultimately, from a health care organizational standpoint, it has been shown that feedback on discharge failures is critical. Without understanding each and all of the contributing elements to the patient’s requirement for rehospitalization, performance improvement in the organization cannot occur. This is another key value of strong administrative support systems – to separate the suspected versus actually factors affecting outcome. The feedback of elements of success and failure are vital to the administrative process of continuous quality improvement.

Another area of focus for the USC Keck Pioneer ACO concerns provision of optimal end of life care. Studies have shown that frequently highly expensive and knowingly ineffective oncology treatment is provided within the last six months of life. Cancer treatment is highly variable amongst both individual providers and varying geographical regions (47). These studies also show that cancer treatment might be one of the largest factors in wasteful futile care. Oncology treatment represents a significant portion of total Medicare spending and may represent an unnecessary and futile component of end of life care (47).

Studies have shown that high end of life costs often stem from both patients and providers' lack of education relative to other care options. Primary care physicians and specialists are sometimes either limited in their knowledge of palliative care, other end of life options or lacking supportive resources in this area (48). Keck should continue to educate its primary care physicians, specialists and residents as to the nature and benefits of palliative care. Keck primary care physicians should make every effort possible to maintain regular follow up visits with patients who are approaching end of life. The expected benefits would be lower rates of avoidable hospitalizations, less futile care, lower total costs of care and higher likelihood of enrollment in palliative and/or hospice programs (49). Further emphasis on patient education regarding the lack of benefits for aggressive end of life health interventions, might be expected to lower cost of care while maintaining patient quality of life (50). Increased emphasis on utilization of POLST forms, advanced directives and palliative care programs should be a point of continued and ongoing emphasis (50). Studies have shown that education of physicians and patients regarding end of life care may produce significant benefits (48).

Furthermore, nationwide the concept of palliative care is sometimes poorly understood by both physicians and patients. Availability of both outpatient and inpatient palliative care services are often lacking with inadequate financial reimbursement.

In a recent review of Medicare data from the Dartmouth Atlas Project, end of life care remains expensive and in many ways still futile (51). While patients are less likely to die in the ICU or hospital setting than previously, these health care cost savings have been offset by other physician ordered futile and frequently expensive treatment choices (51). End of life care costs will not be truly reduced until new highly expensive and yet often futile treatment options [frequently chemotherapy in terminal cancer patients] are reduced (51).

Studies have shown that there are a number of factors which drive higher than expected Medicare costs (52). In particular for the Keck ACO, the lack of an available primary care physician, inadequate timely access to outpatient care, poor communication between providers, suboptimal transitions of care and provision of futile treatment were identified as just a few of the factors that limit quality and produce higher than desired healthcare costs. Identifying and overcoming these issues alone should produce significant benefits.

The Vital Importance of Delivering Care at The Right Time:

At the USC Keck Pioneer ACO, it is of vital importance that care is delivered at the right time. The timing of care truly impacts quality and cost. For example, the ability to arrange qualified and timely follow-up care creates an environment of avoidable disease and fewer complications (53). The ability to recognize complications early in the post-discharge period create a lower likelihood for small problems to turn into larger ones, resulting in fewer unnecessary repeat hospitalizations. For surgical patients, the challenges may be different, but adequate and timely follow-up care still remains critical. While some complications of surgery may become immediately apparent prior to discharge, others are more silent and only clinically apparent and significant until well after discharge. The USC Keck Pioneer ACO must ensure that it provides care at the right time to reduce the likelihood of complications and detrimental health outcomes.

Another key component to reducing avoidable complications and costs is that of very timely post-discharge outpatient follow-up. Ensuring patients see their primary care physician (or any physician) as soon as possible after discharge is critical. This allows for rapid detection of medication confusion, early post-discharge complications and an assessment of issues that may prevent recovery in the home setting. As such, timely post-discharge physician follow up visits improve the quality of care delivered. From a review of Keck ACO data, this is an area ripe for significant improvement.

As Table IV shows, only a minority of discharged patients receive outpatient follow up within the critical and vulnerable seven days following discharge (5). The spectrum of follow-up periods seen by Keck ACO patients show significant room for improvement.

Timing for the USC Keck Pioneer ACO is of great importance in regard to not only dealing with readmissions, but also in initiating alternatives for palliative or end of life care. Studies have shown that while enrollment in hospice has become a more popular option, the costs of healthcare immediately prior to enrolling in hospice remains unnecessarily high (50). In many of the deceased Keck ACO patients, one can identify where initiation of palliative or hospice care sooner may have benefitted the patient's quality of life, while not squandering unnecessary healthcare resources and spending.

In these patients, the outcome would have been the same. The transitions in these patient's end of life care would have been smoother, more humane and less costly.

The benefits of palliative care have been shown (34). In one study, patients who experienced three skilled nursing facility admissions within six months underwent a palliative care consultation. These patients were subsequently more likely to ultimately enter hospice, less likely to experience acute hospital readmissions and resulted in lower Medicare spending (34). Family members were pleased with the care provided. If transitions to palliative or hospice care occurred sooner or if patients were educated regarding potentially futile treatment options, significant cost and quality of life benefits would be produced. (50). The timing of patient education regarding treatment alternatives, palliative care or hospice enrollment, truly matters to Keck ACO patients.

At the USC Keck ACO, it is of vital importance that care is delivered at the right time. Sometimes the correct timing implies prompt care that recognizes complications early, and lessens avoidable deterioration or hospitalization. In other cases, the concept of "right time" implies when to receive or not receive expensive and medically aggressive treatments. Lastly, right time implies knowing when to provide humane and supportive end of life measures.

Obtaining Care at the Right Place Really Matters:

To help ensure optimal clinical outcomes, the USC Keck Pioneer ACO must ensure that their patients are obtaining care at the “right place.” In some cases, this will mean the development of new resources. In other cases, determination of the optimal place for care from existing resources will be vital. Health care organizations like the USC Keck Pioneer ACO may need to identify or develop additional patient resources to specifically overcome barriers which impair quality while driving cost of care up.

As seen in table IV, timely post-discharge follow-up is a significant issue for previously hospitalized Keck patients. While the reasons for not receiving timely post-discharge outpatient follow-up may be many, one cannot deny a simple fact. Failing to receive a post-discharge follow-up visit within the critical and vulnerable seven day period following discharge, leads to increased complications, readmissions and costs. This may be exaggerated in a Medicare ACO when care is scattered and sometimes is unclear who should take primary responsibility.

One alternative would be the formation of a Keck discharge clinic. The responsibility of this clinic would be to see all discharged patients promptly, within no more than seven days following discharge. As such, this discharge clinic can ensure more than just timely follow-up. In some cases, resources such as case management, social work and pharmacology might be readily available to ensure that the transition from inpatient to outpatient care occur smoothly. The need for additional home health, DME and social work may only become apparent following discharge. Medication

reconciliation of new or altered discharge medication lists can be performed.

Additionally, the discharge clinic might facilitate the flow of communication from the inpatient setting to subsequent outpatient providers. Patients may be seen in the Keck discharge clinic regardless of site of prior hospitalization. As such, the discharge clinic might provide the type of resources, time and facilitated communication that otherwise would not be available on a busy provider's schedule. The role of the discharge clinic may continue for a number of subsequent visits until the patient is ready for transition to the next less intensive level of outpatient follow-up care.

Studies have shown that the building and staffing of a discharge clinic can significantly reduce hospital readmissions (13). In this setting at Hoag Hospital in Newport Beach, elements of medication reconciliation, detection of early complications and evaluation for other post-discharge resources led to a nearly 50% reduction in 30 day hospital readmission rates (55). As a bridge between hospital and the traditional outpatient follow-up, it serves as an important source of care during the first few vulnerable weeks after discharge. Given the frequent gaps in care and communication that occur following discharge, these efforts to maintain continuity of care and provide high quality care (instead of otherwise unpredictable physician follow-up), have been shown to be highly effective in reducing readmissions (13).

As important as improving quality and lowering cost, discharge clinics receive high marks by patients and providers alike. Patients appreciate the timely and smooth transition. Providers appreciate not having to determine what may have occurred during a recent hospitalization, and what additional care is needed, in a fifteen or twenty

minute appointment block. Where discharge clinics have been implemented, reviews are positive by all involved.

To ensure that the patients of the USC Keck Pioneer ACO receive optimal care, Keck will need to either develop or select the best and cost-efficient skilled nursing facilities to refer their patients to. However, among skilled nursing facilities across the US, there are great variations in the provision of extra Medicare reimbursement beyond the daily Medicare per diem for many high intensity services (56). In some cases, these high intensity services are cost-effective, lowering future length of stay, rates of readmission and other complications (56). In other circumstances, these additional charges merely increase Medicare reimbursement for the facility while providing little clinical benefit (56). In an analysis of billings by skilled nursing facilities, evidence suggests that patterns of upcoding exist which cannot be explained merely by the patient's underlying medical condition (22).

The ability of clinical case management, for example, to recognize and coordinate the appropriate level of care upon discharge is also critical: the case managers role is to insure that the patient is discharged at the optimal time, and to the next optimal level of care. Determining carefully and thoughtfully whether a patient should be discharged to a sub-acute facility, a skilled nursing hospital, a custodial facility or home, has been shown to lower the rates of readmission (14). The case managers who help coordinate Keck ACO patients play an important role by ensuring that patients are correctly transitioned to the next appropriate level and place of care.

Follow-up by the Keck case managers following discharge with the skilled nursing facility could be important in overcoming errors of communication or other

clinically relevant information (43). Doing so would be expected to improve outcomes and lower cost of care (37). Direct communications between the discharging Keck hospital physicians and the accepting skilled nursing facility doctors is currently lacking and could be of great value in communicating vital aspects of the patient's care plan.

The USC Keck Pioneer ACO will want to make sure to identify the skilled nursing facilities that provide high value and represent desirable alternatives for Medicare ACO patients when placement into a skilled or non-skilled nursing facility is necessary (34). The question remains, how to best choose the facility? Quality ratings of skilled and non-skilled facilities do exist, but they may not be useful in determining the optimal place for the Keck patients. While "Nursing Home Compare" quality ratings are intended to imply the overall quality of various skilled nursing facilities across the US, these score do not correlate well with the outcome for particular individual medical conditions (57). Skilled nursing facilities that have particular treatment programs and educational awareness for patients with heart failure show shorter length of stay, lower overall cost, lower rates of readmission and better clinical outcomes (58). Also, skilled nursing facilities with higher levels of qualified staff result in fewer hospital readmissions (59). The USC Keck Pioneer ACO should also identify preferential skilled nursing facilities that specialize in or have greater competency for patients with certain medical conditions. Keck should seek to identify skilled nursing facilities with higher RN and PT ratios for use with patients whom those skills would be particularly useful for a subset of their patient discharges. Facilities with high levels of P.T. staffing and rehab sophistication might be best suited for example, for patients discharged after orthopedic injuries or joint replacements (60). Programs that provide integrated post-discharge care from

skilled nursing facilities and provide greater communication and continuity with post-skilled nursing facility health care providers reduces the risk for avoidable complications (59).

Overall, larger skilled nursing facilities tend to show lower rates of complications and hospital readmissions (26). These facilities which utilize higher levels of registered nurses and physical therapists and treat a high volume of patients resulted in shorter skilled nursing facility lengths of stay, lower numbers of hospital readmissions and fewer emergency department visits (60). Those facilities with greater physical therapy staffing levels were particularly beneficial to those patients with the greatest physical therapy needs (60). There are, however, many exceptions to this and a facility's volume of care is not alone the best predictor of skilled nursing facility care (26).

Ultimately, outcome data should drive referral choice. Compiling data on various skilled and non-skilled facilities within the Heritage Provider Network, possibly in association with other Los Angeles area Medicare ACO and MSSP programs, may create a significant database for evaluation. As such, determination of facilities with lower historic complication rates, readmission rates and costs might be determined for various risk-adjusted conditions. Currently the choice of skilled and non-skilled facilities is heavily influenced by hospital care managers who are swayed by marketing efforts and their own limited experience. Data evaluation may truly establish optimal referral choices. Ultimately, physicians, case managers, patients and their family should be provided the names of these preferred facilities, which would benefit all, both in terms of cost and quality.

Inpatient resources at Keck Hospital may need development or expansion. Studies have shown that development of inpatient palliative care units facilitate discharge to outpatient palliative or hospice care settings (30).

Keck physicians in discussion with their hospital partners should consider discussion of dedicated palliative care beds with palliative oriented nurses to facilitate transition to outpatient palliative and hospice care and therefore lowering of unnecessary end of life costs and care. Important discussions with physicians who offer extremely expensive treatment options in the final and often futile stages of care will be important (51). Education regarding utilization of high tech and very expensive treatment options that are not expected to produce significant life extension and quality of life must be carried out (51). Understanding the varying philosophies regarding Keck providers as related to EOL care will help to design individually targeted educational campaigns for lower cost and higher quality of life alternatives (16).

This is important as palliative care and pre-palliative care programs can significantly reduce the cost of care for seriously ill patients while improving patient's and family's overall satisfaction with care delivered (49). It is important that time and resources are devoted to discussions of appropriate future care: the appropriate levels of future hospital intervention, advanced directives of care, the possible benefits of palliative care and even an appropriate discussion regarding the benefits of hospice. These types of discussions are difficult, time consuming and can become very costly.

At Keck, even allocation of a portion of an existing inpatient medical floor to that of being a "palliative care unit" might provide concentrations of case managers, social workers and nurses who truly understand concepts regarding end of life care. Placing

appropriate resources in this unit allows for immersion by appropriate staff and resources.

To help ensure optimal clinical outcomes, the USC Keck Pioneer ACO must ensure that their patients are obtaining care at the right place. As examples, the development of post-discharge clinics, special care centers, palliative care units and the identification of preferred skilled and non-skilled nursing facilities, are all examples of interventions which help the patient receive their care in the “right place.” Receiving care in the ideal location will improve quality while lowering total cost of care. Ultimately receiving care in the “right place” is integral to other issues of timing, quality and overall cost for Medicare ACO patients.

Receiving Care From the Right People Makes A Difference:

Ultimately, for healthcare costs to be lower, and quality of care improved, the “right people” must be involved in the care of Medicare ACO patients. Sometimes these people are the physicians who directly provide the medical decisions, advice or treatment. In other circumstances, the “right people” represent the leadership team which designs, and implements the programs which will hopefully advance the objectives of an accountable care organization.

At the physician level, Medicare suffers from a fundamental flaw. Reimbursements of physicians are perversely the same regardless of the skill of care provided, or the quality of outcomes achieved. For the most part, Medicare reimburses for volume of care, not value of care. And ironically, physicians receive reimbursement not only for marginal care, but also for treatment of complications that may directly emanate from their marginal care.

Involvement of primary care physicians shortly after discharge also improves the quality and cost of care. Post-discharge follow-up with a specialist or sub-specialist alone is not likely to address the wide variety of issues that the recently hospitalized frail and elderly suffer from. In addition, a strong and consistent relationship with a primary care physician is equally important to patients at other critical times, such as at end of life. Accordingly, the role of the primary care physician is key in reducing avoidable complications and reducing futile care. One particular study demonstrated that medical groups with a strong primary care focus produce higher-quality care at a

lower total cost (62). Keck should continuously encourage its patients to have a strong relationship with a qualified primary care physician, and should attempt to expand its own primary care base.

For this reason, it is critical that the ACO truly understand which providers offer the optimal value for its patients, with the lowest direct and indirect cost relative to quality of outcomes. If the USC Keck Pioneer ACO narrowed the referral base to those physicians with optimal skills for the particular medical condition, significant improvements in outcomes, lowering of complications, the need for subsequent skilled nursing facility care, and lowered rates of readmission would be expected (63).

For example, treatment of similar spine disorders varies from non-surgical to surgical treatment (64). The cost, quality and outcome of various treatment alternatives can vary greatly (64). Similarly in oncology, when oncologists are reimbursed more for the provision of aggressive treatment, as opposed to the most appropriate and humane, than perverse incentives are created. Even when not conscious, the individual perspective of an oncologist towards the concepts of palliative or hospice care, can significantly impact cost and quality of care delivered. In this example, as in many others, it would make great sense to understand the total cost of care and quality of care provided by various providers.

Studies have shown that the variation among providers in these two metrics (total cost of care and quality) is great. To the extent that referring physicians might have access to this data, than referral decisions might be based upon information that is in the best interests of patients, the ACO and society as a whole. Additionally, emphasizing referrals based upon cost and quality would have spill-over benefits in

terms of driving improvement in lower performing providers. Since Keck ACO patients frequently live and receive care outside of Keck's local region, identifying providers in adjoining areas who can provide high-quality care at lower than average cost should be a priority for USC's ACO. In general, moving care from the lowest performing providers to the highest performing providers would have immense cost and quality benefits in many aspects of healthcare delivery.

Organizationally, the "right people" also implies the leadership to solve problems, implement new programs, overcome barriers and promote a care environment with circumstances for high-value care. Foremost, those involved in leadership must impart cultural transformation on those who care for patients in the ACO. Those who provide care must be convinced that the adoption of shared values and sometimes new and differing methods of care will be for the best. Transforming culture of care for Medicare patients will not be easy, as the tendency to deliver healthcare by the same persons, in the same manner, limited by the same personal and logistical barriers is difficult. This may be especially challenging as there are components of the Keck ACO delivery system which actually benefit from the current inefficient, costly and not always best status quo.

The ability to launch concepts of continuous clinical improvement will fall on the shoulders of operational leadership, and must flow down to all involved (14). ACO management must be able to recruit, retain, and influence those who will be key to the cultural and clinical transformation which leadership must depend upon it, if it is to lower costs and improve quality.

Ultimately for patients, receiving care from the "right people" makes a significant difference. Sometimes these "right people" are those that directly provide, influence or

direct clinical decisions and treatment (46). Equally important, however, the “right people” involved in a patient’s care, are sometimes never seen by the patient. These “right people” are those that design, influence or implement the systems or culture that aspires to the highest quality of care, at the lowest possible cost. Collectively, without these people influencing healthcare delivery, no improvements in cost or quality are possible.

Conclusion and Possible Process Improvement Recommendations for the Keck Pioneer Medicare ACO:

As a University Provost Undergraduate Research Fellow during the summer of 2014, I was able to review many operational aspects of USC Keck's involvement in the Pioneer Medicare Accountable Care Program. The goal of this program is to develop innovations that allow for lowering total cost of care for Medicare recipients, while simultaneously improving quality metrics.

Based upon widely published research, significant variations in Medicare spending exist throughout the nation. And relative to many group's performance in the Medicare Advantage program, clearly there is significant room for improvement in terms of cost and quality of outcomes. Currently the Medicare Pioneer Accountable Care program exists at an awkward and somewhat ineffective stage. While the goals may be lofty, significant funding does not exist to truly deliver new and innovative programs. As Medicare payments for services continue unchanged, with physicians having little incentive to change behavior. Currently, the Pioneer ACO does not provide a significant financial incentive to change provider mindset from volume to value. Similarly, hospitals may not see the benefits of reduction in utilization or funding additional programs, without a share in savings.

Nevertheless, change appears to be coming. Medicare Advantage (and global capitation for care) already accounts for a significant volume of current Medicare patients, and appears to be growing with new Medicare enrollees. Similarly

Commercial fee for service insurance is progressively looking for its own accountable care model; either in terms of reimbursement or rewards or in exclusion from narrow networks.

Therefore, the recommendations I have for the Keck Pioneer ACO are broad, and applicable to these patients as well as others. Reviewing raw cost data as well as clinical observations from retrospective chart review, I was able to place USC's operational performance in the context of research and evidence based recommendations which have been shown to be beneficial.

My recommendations fall into five categories of concentration: providing the right care, at the right cost, at the right place, by the right people. As a generality, if every aspect of care is focused on these general goals (right cost, right care, right place right people), then cost and quality improvements will surely follow.

- ✓ Identify and track patients at greatest risk for being near end of life. This group includes patients with terminal and near terminal malignancies, patients with underlying medical circumstances which place them at risk for futile and expensive care. For this group specifically, look to develop patient care coordinators to carefully follow and help patients navigate through otherwise costly options.
- ✓ Possibly in association with other provider groups, analyze data on cost versus outcome measures of regional home health, DME and skilled nursing providers. Developed preferred or suggested referral lists for those providers who have demonstrated higher than average quality, at lower than average cost.

- ✓ Attempt efforts to ensure that high risk patients have established primary care providers.
- ✓ Assess Keck specific issues leading to hospital readmissions. Develop process improvement teams which seek to create a cycle of continuous process improvement to lower rates of unintended hospital readmissions.
- ✓ Look to develop a more comprehensive discharge process, with development of intensive and multi-disciplinary home health resources for patients at high risk for readmission or complications.
- ✓ Seek possible discharge risk assessment software to stratify patients at greatest risk for readmission, and therefore in greatest need for close outpatient follow-up and deployment of significant home health or skilled nursing resources.
- ✓ Analyze outcome data in an attempt to develop lists of skilled nursing and home health services that have demonstrated higher competency for the treatment of patients with specific health conditions. Publicize internally these disease specific providers for increased and preferential referral.
- ✓ Consider development of a discharge clinic: To facilitate post-discharge follow-up appointments at a time of less than seven days following discharge, and to facilitate involvement of case management, pharmacy, home health and other resources at time of visit. Discharge clinic appointments would allow for obtainment of appropriate hospital information to allow for adequate future communication of pertinent and relevant clinical information to subsequent

providers. Close follow-up visits might continue at the discharge clinic until the patient is stable to be transitioned to his next level of outpatient follow-up.

- ✓ Consider expansion of the primary care base at Keck, with its primary care providers participating in Medicare Advantage for global capitation. This will create new organizational mindset which move from volume of care to value of care.
- ✓ Consider development of special care clinics, which care for high acuity Medicare patients with medical issues that many specialties or needs. This clinic would be the internal high acuity clinic which allows for care of patients that cannot be successfully managed in a limited primary care visit setting. This clinic would allow for close outpatient follow up of patients requiring infusions, close laboratory monitoring, longer office visit durations, access to case management and other ancillary services all in one setting. This special care clinic would be expected to decrease avoidable hospitalizations significantly, and would take pressure off primary care physicians who don't have the time in their schedule to manage these complex patients closely and frequently over a short duration of time.
- ✓ Integrate access to palliative care and hospice agencies within the special care and discharge clinics to facilitate discussion of these issues at time of visit, and ease of enrollment.
- ✓ Increase availability of POLST forms, and consider formal offering of these forms to patients in the primary care setting, special care clinics, discharge clinics, and

patients who reside in nursing homes, assisted living facilities, and prior to transfer to skilled nursing facilities.

- ✓ Increase availability of educational materials for patients enrolled in the ACO relative to the nature of palliative care, advanced directives, POLST forms, and hospice care.
- ✓ Consider educational opportunities for USC faculty and residents on high value care; highlighting examples of failures including hospital readmissions, futile care, and patients receiving expensive care without associated value.
- ✓ Create a care coordination committee where physicians might refer particular patients for assistance and advice, who represent particular challenges based upon advanced disease, frailty, economics, language, culture or understanding of disease, and therefore over-utilize resources, seek inappropriate care, or represent particular management challenges.
- ✓ Consider development of new financial and other incentives for physician providers to motivate healthcare cost savings and process improvement.
- ✓ Discuss with hospital representative the feasibility of creation of a dedicated in-patient palliative care unit to facilitate transition from aggressive and active care, to palliative or hospice care while hospitalized.
- ✓ Follow and share with physician staff metrics of hospital readmissions rates, total cost of care, time to post discharge follow-up visits, patients with an active advanced directives or active POLST forms in effect, etc.

- ✓ Explore IT options to increase receipt of clinical information when ACO patients are cared for outside of the USC system.
- ✓ Follow and share compliance with hospital and out-patient metrics related to evidence based best care practices for Keck ACO patients.
- ✓ Explore health risk assessment tools to stratify all ACO patients, and develop lists of patients at risk for near-term high medical needs.
- ✓ Develop list of unmanaged patients within the ACO, and attempt to engage them with strong primary care providers at Keck.
- ✓ Look to use commercial software such as Crimson, to develop lists of providers who provide optimal care at a lower than average risk adjusted cost.
- ✓ Consider formation of discharge case conference to understand failures of discharge planning, and understand institutional changes that might be made to improve future outcomes.
- ✓ Look to fund 24 hour per day, 7 day per week out-patient patient care advisement to offer lower cost suggestions for patients with acute needs. For example referral to a local panel of urgent care facilities (as opposed to ER utilization for clinical complaints) that meet pre-defined criteria (for example patients complaining of bronchitis symptoms, UTI symptoms, minor trauma, etc) outside of regular office hours.
- ✓ Look to development of post-discharge case management to follow up on high risk discharges, whether they are to home or skilled nursing facilities.

Outpatient case management should be available 24 hours per day to deal with potentially avoidable issues at home.

- ✓ Encourage formal communication between discharging physicians and subsequent providers at the next transition of care.
- ✓ Develop staff that might perform telephone medication reconciliation with the patient in their home the day following hospital discharge.
- ✓ Engage oncology providers with ACO case management to facilitate discussions relative to patients who have failed initial chemotherapy, or who have advanced disease.
- ✓ Increase availability of case management, social work, mental health providers, or palliative care representatives in the out-patient setting, to meet with particular patients at time of their primary care or specialty out-patient follow up visits, for patients in whom case management, social work services, mental health or palliative care assistance might be highly desirable. Availability of these options at time of office visit would be expected to improve patient's quality of care, while lowering cost.
- ✓ Look for internal or external providers who offer conservative management programs, such as those dealing with issues like non-surgical chronic back pain management.

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Annotated Bibliography: Literature Reviewed

Ackerly DC, Grabowski DC. Post-Acute Care Reform - Beyond The ACA. N Engl J Med 2014; 370:689-691.

In a perspective article by Ackerly and Grabowski, the point is made that the current methods for payment by CMS do not create the environment for maximal cost effectiveness and do not allow for redistribution of money for currently non-covered benefits which might improve the patient's quality of care with higher patient satisfaction and lower rates of complications and cost. Examples such as bundled payment and global capitation are cited as examples.

Auerbach S. Location, Location, Location; New Atlas Shows That the Medical Treatment You Get May Depend on Where You Get It. The Washington Post. 1996; 7.

In this article by Auerbach, the significant difference in regional treatment variability is discussed. The use of evidence based guidelines instead would likely yield better quality of care and at a lower cost.

Barkley R, Blau M. Cancer Costs Remain A Priority: Innovators Apply Accountable Care To Oncology Redesigns. Managed Healthcare Executive. 2013;23(1):26.

Oncology care is highly variable amongst both individual providers and geographical regions. Oncology treatment represents a significant portion of total Medicare spending and may represent a key component of end of life care.

Berenson RA, Paulus RA, Kalman NS. Medicare's Readmissions-Reduction Program – A Positive Alternative. *New Engl J Med*, Apr 2012;266(15):1364-1365.

In a literature review by Dr. Robert Berenson, Dr. Ronald Paulus, and Noah Kalman, it was emphasized that enacting penalties for readmissions generates a more significant incentive for hospitals to desire to pursue readmission reductions programs. These penalties are important as under Medicare's DRG payment system, hospitals have no economic incentive to reduce readmissions.

Berkowitz RE, Jones RN, Rieder R, et al. Improving Disposition Outcomes For Patients In A Geriatric Skilled Nursing Facility. *JAGS*. 2011;59:1130-1136.

A palliative care implementation program was implemented within a skilled nursing facility setting. Patients who experienced three skilled nursing facility admissions within six months underwent a palliative care consultation. These patients were more likely to ultimately enter hospice care, less likely to experience acute hospital readmissions, and resulted in lower Medicare spending.

Berry L, Kent S. Management Lessons from Mayo Clinic: Inside One of the World's Most Admired Service Organizations. N.P.: McGraw Hill Professional, 2008. Print.

This book by Berry and others describes the various management practices that have distinguished the Mayo Clinic as a leader in health care.

Boutwell AE, Johnson BM, Rutherford P, et al. An Early Look At A Four-State Initiative To Reduce Avoidable Hospital Readmissions. Health Affairs. Jul 2011;30(7):1272-1282.

According to this article, efforts have been successful in aligning initiatives for the purpose of achieving better results. A number of hospitals as a result have started working together for the purpose of trying to reduce hospital readmissions. The issue of reducing hospital readmissions goes beyond the walls of the hospital; partnerships among the health care community are needed. To help support these partnerships for the purpose of reducing hospital readmissions, financial incentives are necessary to support the cost of investment.

Bowlis JR, Brunt CS. Medicare Skilled Nursing Facility Reimbursement and Upcoding. Health Econ. 2014;23:821-840.

In an analysis of billings by skilled nursing facilities, evidence suggests that patterns of upcoding exist which cannot be explained merely by the patient's underlying medical condition.

Boxer RS, Dolansky MA, Frantz MA, et al. The Bridge Project: Improving Heart Failure Care in Skilled Nursing Facilities. JAMDA. 2012;13(1):83.e1-7.

Evaluation of Cleveland area skilled nursing facilities showed that the identification and treatment of heart failure patients with evidence based best practices for congestive heart failure reduces the rate of cardiac related costs and overall complications. Patients with significant heart disease would be best suited for

discharge to skilled nursing facilities who maintain these types of programs. As such, overall Medicare costs would be expected to be lower for these patients.

Bradke PM, Justice S, Osborne MA , et al. 2012. "Improvements in Care-Transitions: A Case Study of St. Luke's Hospital." *The Brookings Institute* [accessed November 20, 2013]. Available at http://www.brookings.edu/~ /media/centers/health/final_st%20lukes%20case%20study.pdf

In a case study of St. Luke's Hospital, it was demonstrated how this particular entity transformed the way they deliver care to its patients hospitalized with heart failure. As a result of redesigning care pathways, St. Luke's Hospital experienced success in reducing readmissions for these particular patients. St. Luke's new approach was multi-pronged in nature, emphasizing the alignment of providers along a continuum of care, horizontal leadership, rapid and effective learning by all, the development/use of standardized tools with a compatible health information infrastructure.

Butcher L. 2014. "Hospitalists' Role in A Value-Driven Organization." *AHA* [accessed July, 25, 2014]. Available at http://www.hhnmag.com/display/HHN-news-article.dhtml?dcrPath=/templatedata/HF_Common/NewsArticle/data/HHN/Magazine/2014/May/fea-staffing-strategies

In this opinion article by Lola Butcher, the role of dedicated hospitalists in reducing total cost of hospital care and subsequent post discharge care is emphasized.

Caramenico, A. 2013. "Medicare Slaps Two-Thirds of US Hospitals With Readmission Penalties."

Fierce Healthcare [accessed November 21, 2013]. Available at

<http://www.fiercehealthcare.com/story/medicare-slaps-two-thirds-us-hospitals-readmission-penalties/2013-08-05>

An examination of the nation's 5,700 hospitals indicated that 2,225 of these hospitals will experience payment reductions in Medicare reimbursements as a result of Medicare readmission penalties.

Coleman, EA, Parry C, Chalmers S, et al. The Care Transitions Intervention Results of a Randomized Controlled Trial. Arch Intern Med. 2006; 166(17):1822-1828. doi:10.1001/archinte.166.17.1822.

In this analysis, data was collected on randomized patients 65 and older identified at hospitalization those who were to receive an intervention of a transition of care coach as opposed to the usual care they would receive. The study discovered that patients who received the intervention had lower re-hospitalization rates for both 30 and 90 days. If the needs of chronically ill and older patients are met during the transition of care, the rates of subsequent re-hospitalization are reduced.

Decker FH. "Outcomes and Length of Medicare Nursing Home Stays: The Role of Registered Nurses and Physical Therapists." Am J Med Qual. 2008 Nov-Dec;23(6):465-74. doi:

10.1177/1062860608324173.

Examination of over 4,280 skilled nursing facility admissions showed that facilities which utilize higher levels of registered nurses and physical therapists resulted in shorter skilled nursing facility lengths of stay, lower numbers of hospital readmissions, and fewer Emergency Department visits. Those facilities with greater physical therapy staffing levels were particularly beneficial to those patients with the greatest physical therapy needs.

Dellinger P, Townsend SR. Point: Are the Best Patient Outcomes Achieved When ICU Bundles Are Rigorously Adhered To? Yes. Chest. 2013;144(2):372-374. doi:10.1378/chest.13-0846

This editorial by Dellinger and others emphasizes the importance of care bundles when they are applied to patients in the ICU. By standardizing most aspects of ICU care, the reliability of delivery of evidence-based care can improve patient outcomes and reduce incurred costs. Protocols have the ability to minimize inconsistencies.

Digwood G, Lustbader D, Pekmezaris R, et al. The Impact of A Palliative Care Unit on Mortality Rate And Length of Stay For Medical Intensive Care Unit Patients. Palliative and Supportive Care. 2011;9:287-392

This study published in 2011 shows that development of inpatient palliative care units can significantly reduce ICU costs and number of patients dying within the acute hospital setting. The creation of an inpatient palliative care unit facilitated hospital discharges to outpatient palliative care or hospice settings.

Edlin M. ACO Models: Physician-Led Models Seem To Have Several Advantages. Managed Healthcare Executive. Oct 2013:35-36.

This overview of Pioneer ACO results to date suggest that physician led ACOs have a much greater chance of implementing cost saving measures.

Eilbert M, De Coro A, Le J, et al. "Hospital Medicine." Society of Hospital Medicine 8 (2013). Web. 25 July 2014.

In this article published in the journal of hospital medicine, the results of formation of a post discharge clinic were published. In this discharge clinic, high risk patients were seen shortly following discharge and received multi disciplinary evaluation and intervention. Through the use of this post discharge clinic, 30 day hospital readmission rates were reduced by nearly 50%.

Engel N. Paying for Care Episodes and Care Coordination. N Engl J Med 2007; 356:1166-1168.

A literature review by Dr. Karen Davis expressed that better health outcomes, lower total costs, and less medical errors are more likely if patients have a regular source of care, especially with the same physician. New payment methods will be warranted to discourage the fragmentation of the health care system and the dispersion of care by multiple physicians.

Epstein AM, Jha AK, Orav EJ. The Relationship Between Hospital Admission Rates and Rehospitalizations. N Engl J Med Dec 2011;265(24):2287-2295.

An evaluation of national Medicare Provider Analysis and Review data was used to calculate for each local hospital the 30, 60, and 90 day readmission rates for the patients diagnosed with congestive heart failure or pneumonia that are discharged from the hospital.

Evans M. Limited Medicare ACO Quality Data Show Sharp Variations in Performance. Modern Healthcare. May 2014;44(18):23-25.

In this article from Modern Healthcare, the current challenges of obtaining quality data from CMS is outlined and reviewed.

Facts About Rising Healthcare Costs. Aetna, n.d. Web. 22 Nov. 2013.

According to National Health Expenditure data, total health care spending in the United States is expected to reach 4.8 trillion dollars in 2021. According to the article, some of the source for these significant health care expenditures are: new medical technology, high provider prices, increases in hospital costs, excessive spending due to unnecessary tests and procedures, unhealthy lifestyles, taxes, and having an aging population. Aetna has evaluated the problem of spiraling health care costs, and has contributed a few solutions that they feel can make a difference.

Fisher ES, Wennberg DE, Stukel TA, et al. The Implications of Regional Variations in Medicare Spending. Part 2: Health Outcomes and Satisfaction With Care. Ann Intern Med 2003;138:288-298.

Findings by Elliot Fischer and others confirm that there is little relationship between cost of care for Medicare patients and the quality of care they receive.

Forni A, Chu HT, Fanikos J. Technology Utilization To Prevent Medication Errors. Curr drug saf. 2010 Jan;5(1):13-8.

System-wide improvements have become the focus of efforts to prevent medication errors, which can lead to iatrogenic illnesses. One method identified as a way to try to reduce medication errors as well as improve the quality of care is through health information technology. Various electronic developments in health information technology can help reduce errors in medication dispensing and administration, improve communication regarding critical changes in a patient's condition, alert the prescribing physicians of potential drug interactions/allergies, and much more.

Fortinsky RH, Madigan EA, Sheehan TJ, et al. Risk Factors For Hospitalization in A National Sample of Medicare Home Health Care Patients. J Appl Gerontol. 2014;33(4):474-493.

This article evaluated 374,000 Medicare patients receiving home health and identified risk factors while under home health care that predicted subsequent acute hospitalization. Home Health providers that identify particular risk factors might expose patients at risk for acute hospitalization. Identifying these risk factors and targeting care may lower the risk of hospitalization.

Geilfuss II C F. United States: American Hospital Association Recommends Revisions To Medicare ACO Models. Mondaq Business Briefing. (2014). Web. 25 July 2014.

In this opinion article by Geilfuss, the point is made that hospitals currently have little to gain by reducing hospital utilization and hospital services. The American Hospital Association points out that truly comprehensive programs to reduce cost of care and quality of care must have payment methods that incentivize hospitals to lower total cost of care and allow their financial participation in ACO shared savings and payment methodologies.

Geilfuss II C F, Vernaglia LW. United States: CMS Releases Information On Success of Shared Savings Programs: Early Results Mixed and Inconclusive. Mondaq Business Briefing (2014). Web. 25 July 2014.

In this news release, the initial financial performance of various participants in the Pioneer ACO program are summarized. While some Pioneer ACO programs realized financial rewards from the lowering of healthcare costs in the program's first year many were not able to achieve sufficient financial savings to meet benchmarks for incentive payments. Given the mixed results, this article points out that greater understanding will be needed to understand the true factors driving success of failure in the Pioneer ACO program.

Geilfuss CFI. Win, Lose, and Push: CMS Announces First Year Results On The Pioneer ACO Program. Mondaq Business Briefing. 2013.

Thirty two organizations across the US were selected to be a part of the Pioneer ACO program. However, after the first year, nine of these organizations decided against continuing to participate the following year. Almost half of the entities that participated received financial bonuses as a result of their performance reducing Medicare costs. In regard to quality measures, Pioneer ACOs did better than the Medicare fee-for-service entities.

Golden AG, Martin S, da Silva M, et al. Care Management And The Transition of Older Adults From A Skilled Nursing Facility Back Into The Community. Care Management Journals. 2011; 12(2):54-59.

A review of literature shows that skilled nursing facilities with higher levels of qualified staff results in fewer hospital readmissions. Programs that provide integrated post discharge care from skilled nursing facilities and provide greater communication and continuity with post skilled nursing facility health care providers reduces the risk for avoidable complications.

Goodman D. Study Examines Trends For Medicare Patients At EOL. Hospice Management Advisor. 2011.

In a recent review of Medicare data from the Dartmouth Atlas Project, end of life care remains expensive and in many ways still futile. While patients are less likely to die in the ICU or hospital setting than previously, these health care cost savings have been offset by other futile and frequently expensive treatment choices. End of life care costs will not be truly reduced until new highly expensive and yet often futile treatment options are reduced in those patients who will not gain significant

extension of life with associated quality.

Gottlieb DJ, Zhou W, Song Y, et al. Prices Don't Drive Regional Medicare Spending Variations. Health Affairs. Mar 2010;29(3):537-543.

Analysis of Medicare spending across the US shows significant variations. Regions of high Medicare costs are largely due to over utilizations of services, higher billing practices, and higher cost for services provided. There is no relationship between cost and quality.

Grabowski DC, Afendulis CC, McGuire TG. Medicare Prospective Payment And The Volume And Intensity of Skilled Nursing Facility Services. J Health Econ. 2011;30:675-684.

A recent journal review of the prospective payment system for skilled nursing facilities found great variability in potential cost. Among skilled nursing facilities across the US, there are great variations in the provision of extra Medicare reimbursement beyond the daily Medicare per diem for many high intensity services. In some cases, these high intensity services are cost effective, lowering future length of stay, rates of readmission, and other complications. In other circumstances, these additional charges merely increase Medicare reimbursement for the facility while providing little clinical benefit.

Grenier MA, Hammill BG, Fonarow GC, et al. Predicting Costs Among Medicare Beneficiaries With Heart Failure. Am J Cardiol. 2012;109:705-711.

Using Medicare skilled nursing facility claims data over a three year period, skilled nursing facilities that have particular treatment programs and educational awareness for patients with heart failure show shorter length of stay, lower overall cost, lower rates of readmission, and better clinical outcomes.

Healy M. "Quiet Passings Don't Come Easy; Medicare Patients are Increasingly Choosing Hospice Care -- But Often Endure Harsh, Futile Treatments First." Los Angeles Times, Feb 6, 2013, A.1.

This report describes how increasingly patients are choosing hospice for their terminal care. In spite of this however, the costs of healthcare immediately prior to enrolling in hospice remains high with still often futile and inappropriate treatments offered or recommended. Transitions of palliative or hospice care sooner or patient education regarding treatments with little expected true clinical benefit would produce significant cost and quality of life benefit.

Hechenbleikner, EM, Makary MA, Sanarov DV, et al. Hospital Readmission By Method of Data Collection. J Am Coll Surg. 2013 Jun;216(6):1150-8. doi:10.1016/j.jamcollsurg.2013.01.057. Epub 2013 Apr 11.

In this study, three different data collection methods were utilized to obtain 30 day unplanned readmission rates and potentially unnecessary readmissions among colorectal patients. It is believed that with improved patient care efforts, approximately 30% of the complications may not have required readmissions. Therefore the reimbursements that are based on readmissions should be standardized to minimize perverse incentives.

Hernandez AF, Greiner MA, Fonarow GC, et al. Relationship Between Early Physician Follow-Up and 30-Day Readmission Among Medicare Beneficiaries Hospitalized For Heart Failure. JAMA; May 5 2010;303(17):1716-1722.

An evaluation of patients 65 years or older diagnosed with heart failure who are discharged to home from hospitals participating in the Organized Program to Initiate Lifesaving Treatment in Hospitalized Patients With Heart Failure and the Get With the Guidelines-Heart Failure quality improvement program. It was concluded that patients who have quicker follow-up rates after they are discharged from the hospital have a reduced risk for 30 day readmission.

Hoffmann, C., and A. Georgiou. 2013. "The Pioneer ACO Program: A Closer Look at the Numbers." Triple Tree [Accessed November 22, 2013]. Available at <http://www.triple-tree.com/blog/2013/09/06/the-pioneer-aco-program-a-closer-look-at-the-numbers/>

According to a literature review composed by Chris Hoffman and Archelle Georgiou, over 100 media reports and press releases were analyzed to get a better understanding of the Pioneer ACO results. From these reports, an early assessment of the first year of Pioneer ACOs indicated that it is unlikely that ACOs can achieve financial success. However, an evaluation of year two is necessary to see if this assessment will stand.

Hogan C, Lunney J, Gabel J, et al. Medicare Beneficiaries' Costs of Care In The Last Year of Life. Health Aff. July 2001;20(4):188-195.

An analysis utilizing the data from the Medicare Current Beneficiary Survey, the National Mortality Followback Survey, and the Medicare claims and eligibility data to profile the costs of care for Medicare beneficiaries in the last year of life. According to the article's conclusions, the high costs of end of life care are similar to the cost of caring for functional impairment and severe illness. To address these high-end of life costs, the study believes that greater coordination of care for the frail and chronically ill is necessary. End of life policies, such as hospice, should be discussed ahead of time.

Indrakanti SS, Weber MH, Takemoto SK, Hu SS, Polly D, Berven SH. Value-based Care in the Management of Spinal Disorders: A Systematic Review of Cost-utility Analysis. Clin Orthop. 2012; 2011;470:1106-1123.

According to this study, due to the significantly high cost associated with treating spinal disorders, the development of cost-utility interventions will be important. Cost, quality, and outcome of various treatment alternatives can vary greatly in regard to the treatment of spinal disorders.

Intervention lowers hospital readmissions. HealthCare Benchmarks and Quality Improvement. AHC Media LLC; 2011.

In this study using Medicare-funded pilot program data, patients 65 and older who received the generated coaching intervention experienced a lower readmission rate than those who did not receive the intervention. The ultimate goal is to help patients be able to reason through a health problem they experience and know that going in to see their primary care physician is ok as opposed to going straight to the hospital.

Jack BW, Chetty VK, Anthony D, et al. A Reengineered Hospital Discharge Program To Decrease Re-Hospitalization: A Randomized Trial. Ann Intern Med, Feb 3 2009;150(3):178-187.

A randomized trial of 749 English speaking hospitalized adults was performed to evaluate the effectiveness of interventions designed to minimize re-hospitalization post discharge. The participants who were subjected to the readmission prevention interventions exhibited lower readmission rates than those who received the usual care.

James J. Medicare's Hospital Readmissions Reduction Program. American Journal of Health-System Pharmacy. 2013;70:654.

Hospitals are concerned that the public reporting of their readmission rates will have an overall financial impact on hospitals' bottom lines. It is hoped that through public reporting that hospitals will pay more attention to coordinating care for the purpose of reducing readmissions.

Jencks SF, Williams MV, Coleman EA. Rehospitalizations Among Patients in The Medicare Fee-for-Service Program. N Engl J Med. 2009;360:1418-1428.

An analysis of Medicare claims data from 2003-2004 evaluated the patterns of re-hospitalization among patients in the Medicare fee-for-service program. Almost one fifth of the 11,855,702 evaluated Medicare beneficiaries who had been discharged from the hospital were shortly readmitted within 30 days. These patterns are significant as re-hospitalizations are both costly and prevalent.

Jha AK, Orav J, Epstein AM. Public Reporting of Discharge Planning And Rates of Readmissions. N Engl J Med, Dec 2009;361(27):2637-2645.

An examination of the September 2008 HQA data base of performance data was used to look at hospital performance of discharge planning. The two ways in which this evaluation was conducted involved looking at the adequacy of documentation of discharge instructions in patient charts, and the experiences as reported by patients as to their perspective on the discharge planning process. The Centers for Medicare and Medicaid services have decided to publically report discharge planning conduct. Conclusions suggest that publically reporting discharge data will be unlikely to cause hospitals to triggers reductions in unnecessary readmissions.

Kangovi S, Grande D. Hospital Readmissions--Not Just A Measure of Quality. JAMA : The Journal of the American Medical Association. 2011;306:1796.

In this literature, hospital readmissions are recognized as both costly and common. The authors address some of the various factors that trigger readmissions, and how leaders in the health care entity can help improve access to care so that readmissions can hopefully be reduced.

Kansagara D, Ramsay RS, Labby D, et al. Post-Discharge Intervention In Vulnerable, Chronically Ill Patients. Journal of Hospital Medicine 2012;7(2):124-130.

In this article published in the Journal of Hospital Medicine, the results of formation of a post discharge clinic were published. In this discharge clinic, high risk patients were seen shortly following discharge and received multi-disciplinary evaluation and intervention. Through the use of this post discharge clinic, 30 day hospital readmissions were reduced by nearly 50%.

Kaplan RM. Variation Between End-of-Life Health Care Costs in Los Angeles and San Diego: Why Are They So Different?" J Palliat Med. 2011;14(2):215-220.

In this summary of a comparison in end of life care between the Los Angeles and San Diego regions, end of life care is significantly more expensive in Los Angeles without any measurable quality of benefit. In the Los Angeles region, those higher health care costs are attributed to non-emergent hospital admissions and longer rates of inpatient stays.

Katz, P. "Intelligent Healthcare." CAPG. May 2014. Web. 19 July 2014.

A presentation in May 2013 summarized a number of the findings to date for ACO and Medicare Shared Savings participants in the social area.

King BJ, Gilmore-Bykovskyi AL, Roiland RA, et al. The Consequences of Poor Communication During Transitions From Hospital To Skilled Nursing Facility: A Qualitative Study. JAGS. 2013;61:1095-1102.

In an examination of skilled nursing facilities in Wisconsin, important medical communication between the acute hospital and the subsequent skilled nursing facility is a common occurrence, resulting in inadequate outcomes and higher costs.

Kocher RP, Adashi EY. Hospital Readmissions And The Affordable Care Act: Paying For Coordinated Quality Care. JAMA: The Journal of The American Medical Association. 2011;306:1794.

In this article by Dr. Kocher and others, various methods launched that intend to reduce hospital readmissions is discussed. It is believed that if there is coordination across the continuum of care, that number of readmissions will go down.

Kripalani S, Jackson AT, Schnipper JL, et al. Promoting Effective Transitions of Care At Hospital Discharge: A Review of Key Issues For Hospitalists. Journal of Hospital Medicine: an official publication of the Society of Hospital Medicine. 2007;2:314-323.

This review by Kripalani discusses the key issues for hospitalists and their potential role in significantly reducing medical errors in the period postdischarge. Effective transitions of care, improved communication between inpatient and outpatient

physicians, effective reconciliation of patient medications, closer medical follow-up of patients, and other methods can reduce discontinuity of care and the potential for adverse events.

Kripalani S, Theobald CN, Anctil B, Vasilevskis EE. Reducing Hospital Readmission Rates: Current Strategies And Future Directions. Annu Rev Med. 2013; 2014;65:471.

In this literature review, the approaches to reduce readmission for patients discharged to home or other locations, the prevalence of hospital readmissions, and the methods to identify the patients that are at high risk for readmission are all summarized. The requirement of public reporting and the enactment of financial penalties for excessive hospital readmission has become a mandate as readmission costs are substantial. For hospitals, if efforts are put in to reduce readmissions, an attractive opportunity arises to improve patient satisfaction, improve clinical quality, as well as reduce cost for preventable readmissions.

Kronman AC, Ash AS, Freund KM, Hanchate A, Emanuel EJ. Can Primary Care Visits Reduce Hospital Utilization Among Medicare Beneficiaries at the End of Life? Journal of General Internal Medicine. 2008;23:1330-1335.

In this study by Kronman and others, the important role of the primary care physicians was shown as it related to end of life care. Increasing the number of primary care visits during the last year of life produces many beneficial effects

including lower rates of avoidable hospitalizations, less futile care, lower total costs of care, and higher likelihood of enrollment in palliative and/or hospice programs.

Landers S. The Future of the Medicare Home Health Program. JAMA. 2013;310(14)1443-1444.

Healthcare expert Steven Landers evaluates the areas of potential benefit and abuse in the United States use of home health services for Medicare patients.

Li Y, Cai X, Lin J, et al. Is Higher Volume of Post-Acute Care Patients Associated With A Lower Rehospitalization Rate in Skilled Nursing Facilities? Med Care Res Rev. 2012;69(1):103-118.

Examination of nursing home minimum data set of Skilled Nursing Facilities around the US between January 1st and September 30th 2008 shows that overall, larger skilled nursing facilities tend to show lower rates of complications and hospital readmissions. There are however many exceptions to this, and a facility's volume of care is not alone the best predictor of skilled nursing facility care.

Mandell LA, Wunderink RG, Anzueto A, et al. Infectious Diseases Society of America/American Thoracic Society Consensus Guidelines on the Management of Community-Acquired Pneumonia in Adults. Clinical Infectious Diseases. 2007;44:S27-S72.

This summary by Mandell and others emphasized the importance of having guidelines to improve the care and clinical outcome of patients that have acquired pneumonia. The ultimate importance of this review is to help educate clinicians on the best treatment guidelines for patients diagnosed with pneumonia.

Mattox, M. The ROI of Patient Engagement: Readmissions Reduction. Axial Exchange, 6 May 2013.

Web. 22 Nov. 2013.

An examination of a generated sample hospital, the literature assumes that more than 2,000 annual admissions will be subject to the penalty. In this simulation, the impact of patient engagement was measured to see the return on investment that it would have on a readmissions reduction program.

McCarthy, D. 2012. University of California, San Francisco Medical Center: Reducing Readmissions through Heart Failure Care Management. *The Commonwealth Fund* [accessed November 23, 2013].

Available at <http://www.commonwealthfund.org/publications/case-studies/2012/nov/university-of-california-san-francisco>

In 2008, the University of California, San Francisco (UCSF) sought to reduce hospital readmissions of elderly patients with heart failure. The program generated to reduce readmissions for this particular patient population required program coordinators to provide adequate follow-up care connections so that patients could successfully transition to skilled nursing care or home, as well as enhanced patient education. With these applied performance improvements over the span of 2 years, UCSF observed a decline in the rates of all-cause heart failure readmissions in the selected target population for both 30 and 90 days post initial hospital discharge. UCSF intends to apply what they learned from this program to be applied to younger patients so that they can achieve the goal of reducing all readmissions.

McCue M. Hospice Patients Could Benefit If Referred Sooner; Discussing Hospice and Palliative Care Improves Patient Satisfaction, Lowers Overall Healthcare Costs. Managed Healthcare Executive. Aug 2009;19(8):20+.

This article describes the importance of palliative care programs in reducing the cost of end of life care while maintaining high patient and family care satisfaction.

McKinney M. Where You Live=How You Die; 'Geography is Destiny' For End-of-Life Care, Which Often is Costly and Aggressive. Modern Healthcare. Nov 2010;40(47):0006-0008.

Analysis of Dartmouth Atlas Medicare data suggests there are significant regional differences in the way end of life care is provided. Utilization of futile health care measures varies greatly by state and by region.

McWilliams, JM, Chernew ME, Zaslavsky AM, et al. Delivery System Integration and Health Care Spending and Quality for Medicare Beneficiaries. JAMA Intern Med. 2013;173(15):1447-1456.

This study demonstrates that medical groups with a strong primary care focus produce higher quality care at a lower total cost.

Moore C, Wisnivesky J, McGinn T, et al. Medical Errors Related To Discontinuity of Care From An Inpatient To An Outpatient Setting. J Gen Intern Med. Aug 2003; 18(8):646-651.

A retrospective analysis of the medical records of 366 randomly selected patients among the 2,139 patients discharged from the medical service indicated that at least forty-nine percent of patients experienced at least one medical error. The

prevalence of these medical errors can be related to the discontinuity of care from the inpatient to the outpatient setting. These trends may also be associated with an increased re-hospitalization risk.

O'Connor M. Hospitalization Among Medicare-Reimbursed Skilled Home Health Recipients." *Home Health Care Management & Practice*. 2012;24(1):27-37.

This summary by O'Connor suggests that targeted medical attention to skilled nursing patients at high risk will reduce complications and chance of repeat hospitalization. Increases in nursing services for these high-risk patients has been shown to improve outcomes and lessen complications. The presence of particular medical conditions warrant increased acuity of care and will lead to a positive return on spending to reduce avoidable complications.

Paulus, S. C. 2008. "Palliative Care: An Ethical Obligation." *Santa Clara University* [accessed November 22, 2013]. Available at <http://www.scu.edu/ethics/practicing/focusareas/medical/palliative.html> .

In this literature review, the author Paulus has found palliative care to have many positive outcomes for hospitalized patients. Palliative care has the potential to improve the quality of life of patients who are suffering from incurable, terminal diseases. Palliative care not only helps with the management of pain/discomfort, but also improves the patient physician communication so that care is better coordinated.

Rau, J. Armed With Bigger Fines, Medicare To Punish 2,225 Hospitals For Excess Readmissions. Kaiser Health News, 2 Aug. 2013. Web. 21 Nov. 2013.

An analysis of the Medicare readmission penalty program is Medicare's greatest effort to reimburse not for merely the number of patients that a healthcare entity treats, but instead, for the quality of their service. Two thirds of eligible hospitals were penalized by Medicare. A major concern of hospitals that has emerged is the uneven impact of these Medicare readmission penalties.

Rau J. Hospitals Face Pressure To Avert Readmissions. NY Times, 26Nov. 2012. Web. 22 Nov. 2013.

A literature review by Jordan Rau discusses the impact that Medicare's new readmission penalties are having on healthcare entities. An intention of the Affordable Care Act is to crack down on excessive readmissions, which will help curb the growth of spending that Medicare is experiencing. According to Rau, the goal is to get hospitals to pay attention to what happens to their patients once they leave the hospital.

Reschovsky JD, Hadley J, Saiontz-Martinez CB, et al. Following The Money: Factors Associated With The Cost of Treating High-Cost Medicare Beneficiaries. Health Serv Res.2011 Aug;46(4):997-1021.

In this analysis of high cost Medicare beneficiaries a number of factors were identified which contribute to higher than expected total cost of care. The lack of a primary care physician for the patient, inadequate timely access to outpatient care,

and poor communication between providers and suboptimal transitions of care were identified as factors in producing higher than expected healthcare costs.

Reschovsky JD, Ghosh A, Stewart KA, et al. Durable Medical Equipment and Home Health Among the Largest Contributors To Area Variations In Use of Medicare Services. Health Affairs. 2012;31(5):956-964.

This summary by Reschovsky and others points out the significant variation throughout the United States in the use of home health and durable medical equipment. Additionally, there are significant variations within the same region in terms of billing by home health, and durable medical equipment providers within the same city. These variations cannot be explained by the patient's underlying medical conditions, and truly represent instances of overutilization and over billing.

Riley GF, Lubitz JD. Long-Term Trends in Medicare Payments In The Last Year of Life. Health Serv Res. 2010;45:565-576.

In an analysis of end of life healthcare costs, spending remains inappropriately high despite an increased focus on palliative and hospice care.

Robinson S, Howie-Esquivel J, Vlahov D. Readmission Risk Factors After Hospital Discharge Among The Elderly. Population health management. 2012;15:338-351.

According to this review, hospital readmission rates of elderly patients demands attention due to its exorbitant cost. A comprehensive framework should be

developed so that the gaps in care can be identified so that there is potential to reduce hospital readmissions among the elderly.

Shaligram A, Smith L, Pallati P, et al. Can Laparoscopy For Colon Resection Reduce The Need For Discharge To Skilled Care Facility? Surg Endosc. 2013;27:4038-4043.

An analysis of 221,294 Medicare patients who underwent colon surgery showed those surgeons with optimal clinical skills during the hospital stay produced fewer complications and lowered the chance that they will require skilled nursing care following discharge.

Shepperd S, Parkes J, McClaran J, et al. Discharge Planning From Hospital To Home. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews. 2010;(1):CD000313.

A review of relevant studies using various data bases focused on the effectiveness of the discharge planning of inpatient beneficiaries. According to this article it is uncertain how discharge planning affects readmission rates, hospital length of stay, cost, and patient health outcomes.

Silow-Carroll S, Edwards JN, Lashbrook A. Reducing Hospital Readmissions: Lessons From Top-Performing Hospitals. Commonwealth Fund pub. 1473 Vol. 5.

Some entities are more successful than others at providing the optimal care that would be less likely to yield a readmission. It appears that the successful hospitals have smoothed out the transitions of care, as well as identified the patients who are at high risk for post discharge complications. However while the patient is still in

the hospital, these entities utilize evidence based best practices in their care pathways, which helps standardize the treatment for a particular diagnosis like pneumonia. The document includes some of the best practices utilized by a few selected successful healthcare entities.

Steg PG, James SK, Atar D, et al. ESC Guidelines For The Management of Acute Myocardial Infarction in Patients Presenting With ST-Segment Elevation. Eur Heart J. 2012;33:2569.

In this review, the management of myocardial infarctions should be based on sound evidence, and derived from conducted clinical trials. Members of a cardiac task force helped contribute to the ESC Guidelines.

Stevenson DG. Growing Pains For The Medicare Hospice Benefit. N Engl J Med. Nov 2012;367(18):1683-1685.

In this article published within the New England Journal of Medicine, the case is made for broader and robust development of palliative care programs as part of comprehensive high quality care.

Squazzo JD. Palliative Care Impact on Quality and Cost. Healthcare Executive. 2013;28(1):26-38.

In this summary of palliative care published in Healthcare Executive, the various clinical and economic benefits of a robust palliative care program are detailed.

“The Hospitalist: With Big Data, Hospitals Try To Solve Big Problems Hospitals Use Analytics To Drive Quality Improvements.” 2013. *The Advisory Board Company* [accessed November 21, 2013].

Available at <http://www.advisory.com/daily-briefing/2013/10/17/the-hospitalist-with-big-data-hospitals-try-to-solve-big-problems>

Crimson is a brand of data mining technology that can assist with assist with clinical decision-making, predict health insurance fraud, and identify high-risk patients. Hospitals now have the ability to analyze their practice in areas like readmissions, chronic diseases, and more. Data mining technology has the potential to drive practice consistency. The goal is to analyze practice patterns of large groups and see where the variability exists, and then analyze the observed variability. However, one of the biggest barriers to this data mining and analysis is physician reluctance. It is of great importance to verify the physician’s understanding of the data, and ensure that they actively utilize the data gleaned in their practice pattern, otherwise it will be futile.

Thomson, RM, Patel CR. Palliative Care Principles Primary Care Physicians Should Know. Primary Care Reports. AHC Media LLC; 2013.

This summary by Thomson emphasized that primary care physicians are sometimes lacking in their knowledge of palliative care and specifically end of life options. The authors emphasize that education of primary care physicians in these areas may produce significant benefit to patients.

Unroe KT, Greiner MA, Colon-Emeric C, et al. Associations Between Published Quality Ratings of Skilled Nursing Facilities and Outcomes of Medicare Beneficiaries With Heart Failure. J Am Dir Assoc. 2012;13:188.e1-188.e6.

An evaluation of 164,672 Medicare skilled nursing facility admissions compared the facility's quality ratings and the outcome of patients receiving treatment at their facilities. While Nursing Home Compare quality, ratings are intended to imply the overall quality of various skilled nursing facilities across the US. These score do not correlate well with the outcome for particular individual medical conditions. Determination of a facility's prior outcome statistics for differing medical conditions and patient populations, may better determine choice of skilled nursing facility utilization based upon a patient's particular circumstances.

Unruh MA, Trivedi AN, Grabowski DC et al. Does Reducing Length of Stay Increase Rehospitalization of Medicare Fee-For-Service Beneficiaries Discharged to Skilled Nursing Facilities. JAGS. 2013;61:1443-1448.

Evaluation of over five years of Medicare claims data between 1999 and 2005 revealed, that reductions in Medicare length of stay can improve hospital profitability but are often associated wither greater needs for post discharge care and readmissions and complications. These problems often stem from inadequate transitions of care and coordination of post hospital services and inadequate facilitation of post discharge outpatient services.

White, Kenneth R., and John R. Griffith. *The Well-Managed Healthcare Organization*. 7th ed. Chicago: AUPHA, 2010. Print.

In this textbook by White and others, the key drivers for success to create high performing healthcare organizations are discussed.

Williams MV. A Requirement To Reduce Readmissions: Take Care of The Patient, Not Just The Disease. JAMA: The Journal of The American Medical Association. 2013;309:394.

US hospital attitudes have changed in regard to coordinating transitions of care. In 2008, financial penalties were placed on hospitals with excessive readmissions of patients hospitalized with pneumonia, chronic heart failure, and acute myocardial infarctions. As a result, programs have been developed to try to reduce readmissions for patients with these three conditions. It is now becoming evident that patient centered approaches are necessary rather than the disease focused approaches which were previously financially rewarded through the fee for service program. However, it was noted that for some readmissions were reoccurring for diagnoses other than the initial hospitalization.